

In Silico Prediction of Aridanin as a Potential Anticancer and Antibacterial Agent

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Abstract

Aridanin, 3-*O*-[β -D-glucopyranosyl-(2'-acetamido)]-3 β -olean-12-en-28-oic acid, isolated from *Tetrapleura tetraptera* is reported to have good potentials for use as anticancer agent, especially against resistant cancers. An in-silico study was carried out to evaluate the binding modes of aridanin/doxorubicin and 6 enzymes involved in cancer chemotherapy. Also, prediction on its possible bioactivities and pharmacokinetic properties were made. Aridanin/doxorubicin enzyme interactions were determined using molecular docking and molecular dynamics simulations to attempt an explanation to its anticancer activity. Predictions of bioactivity, pharmacokinetic properties and bioavailability scores of the molecule were calculated using PASS, SwissADME and pKCSM. The results corroborated previous experimental data, with moldock scores comparable to that of the standard drug and relatively higher binding energies. Accordingly, aridanin theoretically is a better inhibitor of studied enzymes than doxorubicin. The highest inhibition recorded binding energies of -9.9, -9.2, and -10.9 kcal/mol for topoisomerase II alpha, DNA methyltransferase, and DD-peptidase respectively. This suggests that aridanin's anticancer property may be more through interference with DNA-related proteins. In addition, ADMET/PASS anticipated that aridanin is not toxic, had good bioavailability score of 0.56 and may display several different bioactivities. Consequently, aridanin is a potent chemotherapeutic agent against resistant cancers and bacteria that should be considered for further *in vivo* studies.

Key words: Aridanin, doxorubicin, anticancer/antibacterial potentials, Molecular Docking, Molecular Dynamics, pharmacokinetic (ADMET) / PASS predictions.

S.1. Extraction and Isolation of Aridanin.

Tetrapleura tetraptera (Schum. & Thonn) Taub. fruits were obtained from Dschang local market on March 2018. The fruit was identified at the National Herbarium (Yaounde, Cameroon) where voucher specimens were deposited under the reference 12117/SRFCam. The crushed fruits (1230 g) were macerated in dichloromethane-methanol (CH₂Cl₂-MeOH; 1:1; 10 L) for 48 h trice after which it was filtered, filtrate evaporated under vacuum to yield 188.65 g of dark brown paste. The paste was partitioned by a solid liquid process into hexane (5.0 g), ethyl acetate (20.3 g), MeOH (82.24) fractions and a residue 45.69 g. The residue was dissolved in water and extracted with n-BuOH to obtain 40.22 g of n-BuOH fraction. The n-BuOH fraction of *T. tetraptera* (38.23 g), was dissolved in CHCl₃-MeOH (1:1 v/v, 100 mL) and absorbed on 50.00 g of fine silica gel, mounted on a silica gel column packed with 338.0 g of fine silica gel and eluted with CHCl₃-MeOH gradient (100:0, 98:2, 95:5, 93:7, 90:10, 85:15, 80:20, 75:25, 70:30). 320 fractions of 200 mL each were collected and pooled according to their TLC profiles into TtB₁ (1 – 42), TtB₂ (43 – 88), TtB₃ (89 – 168), TtB₄ (169 – 221), TtB₅ (222 – 249), and TtB₆ (250 – 320). Compound **1** (120 mg) was obtained directly from silica gel column of fraction TtB₄ (subfraction 180 – 200) eluted with CHCl₃-MeOH (93:7, 90:10, 85:15) and cleaned by gel filtration on sephadex LH20 using CHCl₃-MeOH (70:30).

Figures

Figure S1. High Resolution Electrospray Magnetic Spectrum of α -aridanin.

Figure S2. IR Spectrum of α -aridanin.

Figure S3. ¹H NMR Spectrum of aridanin.

Figure S4. ^{13}C NMR Spectrum of aridanin.

Figure S5. DEPT135 NMR Spectrum of aridanin.

Figure S6. DEPT90 NMR Spectrum of aridanin.

Figure S7. COSY NMR Spectrum of aridanin.

Figure S8. NOESY NMR Spectrum of aridanin.

Figure S9. HSQC NMR Spectrum of aridanin.

Figure S10. HMBC NMR Spectrum of aridanin

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7.

Interactions
 ■ Unfavorable Bump
 ■ Conventional Hydrogen Bond
 ■ Carbon Hydrogen Bond
 ■ Alkyl

8.

Interactions
 ■ Conventional Hydrogen Bond
 ■ Carbon Hydrogen Bond
 ■ Unfavorable Donor-Donor
 ■ Pi-Anion
 ■ Pi-Sulfur
 ■ Amide-Pi Stacked
 ■ Alkyl
 ■ Pi-Alkyl

9.

Interactions
■ Unfavorable Bump
■ Conventional Hydrogen Bond
■ Alkyl
 Carbon Hydrogen Bond

10.

Interactions
■ Conventional Hydrogen Bond
 Carbon Hydrogen Bond
■ Pi-Pi Stacked
■ Alkyl
■ Pi-Alkyl

11.

Interactions
 Unfavorable Bump
 Conventional Hydrogen Bond
 Carbon Hydrogen Bond
 Alkyl

12.

Interactions
 Unfavorable Bump
 Conventional Hydrogen Bond
 Carbon Hydrogen Bond
 Unfavorable Donor-Donor
 Alkyl
 Pi-Alkyl

13.

Interactions
■ Unfavorable Bump
■ Conventional Hydrogen Bond
■ Carbon Hydrogen Bond
■ Alkyl

14.

Interactions
■ Unfavorable Bump
■ Conventional Hydrogen Bond
■ Carbon Hydrogen Bond
■ Pi-Donor Hydrogen Bond
■ Alkyl
■ Pi-Alkyl
■ Unfavorable Donor-Donor

15.

16.

Tables

Table S1. Interaction categories, types, and distances of molecular insertion of the aridanin molecule with Topoisomerase II alpha

No	Name	Distance	Category	Type	Transmitter	From Chemistry	Receiver	To Chemistry
1	B:TRP62:HE1 - :[001:O6	2.12781	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:TRP62:HE1	H-Donor	:[001:O6	H-Acceptor
2	B:LYS83:HZ3 - :[001:O3	2.70852	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:LYS83:HZ3	H-Donor	:[001:O3	H-Acceptor
3	B:GLN310:HN - :[001:O7	2.51362	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:GLN310:HN	H-Donor	:[001:O7	H-Acceptor
4	:[001:H50 - B:GLU379:OE2	2.82164	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H50	H-Donor	B:GLU379:OE2	H-Acceptor
5	:[001:H58 - B:GLN309:OE1	2.13713	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H58	H-Donor	B:GLN309:OE1	H-Acceptor
6	B:ARG242:HD2 - :[001:O8	2.14938	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:ARG242:HD2	H-Donor	:[001:O8	H-Acceptor
7	B:GLN309:HA - :[001:O7	3.08925	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:GLN309:HA	H-Donor	:[001:O7	H-Acceptor
8	:[001:H55 - B:ALA318:O	2.93196	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H55	H-Donor	B:ALA318:O	H-Acceptor
9	:[001:H59 - B:TYR82	2.14572	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma	:[001:H59	C-H	B:TYR82	Pi-Orbitals
10	B:ILE311 - :[001	5.08215	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	B:ILE311	Alkyl	:[001	Alkyl
11	B:ILE311 - :[001	4.55904	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	B:ILE311	Alkyl	:[001	Alkyl
12	B:ALA318 - :[001	4.18942	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	B:ALA318	Alkyl	:[001	Alkyl
13	:[001:C25 - B:LEU238	5.32389	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C25	Alkyl	B:LEU238	Alkyl
14	:[001:C27 - B:ILE311	4.2827	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C27	Alkyl	B:ILE311	Alkyl
15	B:TRP62 - :[001	4.95567	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP62	Pi-Orbitals	:[001	Alkyl
16	B:TYR82 - :[001:C25	4.86656	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TYR82	Pi-Orbitals	:[001:C25	Alkyl
17	B:PHE308 - :[001:C23	5.15254	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:PHE308	Pi-Orbitals	:[001:C23	Alkyl
18	B:PHE313 - :[001:C27	4.95549	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:PHE313	Pi-Orbitals	:[001:C27	Alkyl

Table S2. Interaction categories, types, and distances of molecular insertion of the doxorubicin molecule with Topoisomerase II alpha

No	Name	Distance	Category	Type	Transmitter	From Chemistry	Receiver	To Chemistry
1	A:TYR72:HH - :[001:O3	2.04431	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:TYR72:HH	H-Donor	: [001:O3	H-Acceptor
2	A:ARG241:HH21 - : [001:O6	2.87627	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:ARG241:HH21	H-Donor	: [001:O6	H-Acceptor
3	A:GLN310:HN - : [001:O1	2.80424	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:GLN310:HN	H-Donor	: [001:O1	H-Acceptor
4	: [001:H11 - A:GLN309:OE1	2.5698	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	: [001:H11	H-Donor	A:GLN309:OE1	H-Acceptor
5	A:ILE311:HA - : [001:O9	2.64755	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:ILE311:HA	H-Donor	: [001:O9	H-Acceptor
6	A:SER320:HA - : [001:O9	2.22074	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:SER320:HA	H-Donor	: [001:O9	H-Acceptor
7	: [001:H10 - A:GLN309:OE1	3.08823	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	: [001:H10	H-Donor	A:GLN309:OE1	H-Acceptor
8	: [001:H16 - A:GLN60:O	1.36441	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	: [001:H16	H-Donor	A:GLN60:O	H-Acceptor
9	: [001:H25 - A:TYR82:OH	3.05842	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	: [001:H25	H-Donor	A:TYR82:OH	H-Acceptor
10	: [001:H26 - A:TYR82:OH	3.06406	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	: [001:H26	H-Donor	A:TYR82:OH	H-Acceptor
11	: [001 - A:MET61	4.82066	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	: [001	Alkyl	A:MET61	Alkyl
12	: [001:C23 - A:MET61	4.59581	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	: [001:C23	Alkyl	A:MET61	Alkyl
13	: [001:C24 - A:MET61	4.04406	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	: [001:C24	Alkyl	A:MET61	Alkyl
14	A:TYR82 - : [001:C24	4.97458	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR82	Pi-Orbitals	: [001:C24	Alkyl
15	: [001 - A:ALA318	3.90519	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	: [001	Pi-Orbitals	A:ALA318	Alkyl
16	: [001 - A:ILE311	5.08729	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	: [001	Pi-Orbitals	A:ILE311	Alkyl
17	: [001 - A:ILE311	5.17853	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	: [001	Pi-Orbitals	A:ILE311	Alkyl

Table S3 . Interaction categories, types, and distances of molecular insertion of the aridanin molecule with p53

No	Name	Distance	Category	Type	Transmitter	From Chemistry	Receiver	To Chemistry
1	:[001:H50 - A:LYS51:O	2.41081	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H50	H-Donor	A:LYS51:O	H-Acceptor
2	:[001:H51 - B:GLU28:OE1	2.49631	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H51	H-Donor	B:GLU28:OE1	H-Acceptor
3	:[001:H52 - A:LYS51:O	2.37182	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H52	H-Donor	A:LYS51:O	H-Acceptor
4	:[001:H57 - B:TRP23:O	2.03104	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H57	H-Donor	B:TRP23:O	H-Acceptor
5	A:PHE55:HA - :[001:O1	2.5873	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:PHE55:HA	H-Donor	:[001:O1	H-Acceptor
6	A:PHE55:HA - :[001:O2	3.01378	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:PHE55:HA	H-Donor	:[001:O2	H-Acceptor
7	:[001:H54 - B:TRP23:O	2.44073	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H54	H-Donor	B:TRP23:O	H-Acceptor
8	:[001:H56 - B:GLU28:OE1	3.09145	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H56	H-Donor	B:GLU28:OE1	H-Acceptor
9	B:LYS24 - :[001	5.12022	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	B:LYS24	Alkyl	:[001	Alkyl
10	:[001:C27 - A:MET62	5.28753	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C27	Alkyl	A:MET62	Alkyl
11	A:PHE55 - :[001	4.82551	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE55	Pi-Orbitals	:[001	Alkyl
12	A:PHE55 - :[001	4.88185	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE55	Pi-Orbitals	:[001	Alkyl

Table S4. Interaction categories, types, and distances of molecular insertion of the doxorubicin molecule with p53

No	Name	Distance	Category	Type	Transmitter	From Chemistry	Receiver	To Chemistry
1	A:GLN59:HE22 - :[001:O9	2.39149	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:GLN59:HE22	H-Donor	:[001:O9	H-Acceptor
2	:[001:H11 - A:LYS51:O	2.1041	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H11	H-Donor	A:LYS51:O	H-Acceptor
3	:[001:H12 - B:LEU26:O	2.3737	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H12	H-Donor	B:LEU26:O	H-Acceptor
4	:[001:H29 - A:LEU54:O	2.39085	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H29	H-Donor	A:LEU54:O	H-Acceptor
5	A:LYS51:HA - :[001:O11	2.69444	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:LYS51:HA	H-Donor	:[001:O11	H-Acceptor
6	B:TRP23:HD1 - :[001:O8	1.93934	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:TRP23:HD1	H-Donor	:[001:O8	H-Acceptor
7	:[001:H9 - A:LYS51:O	1.71091	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H9	H-Donor	A:LYS51:O	H-Acceptor
8	:[001:H13 - B:GLU28:OE1	2.43156	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H13	H-Donor	B:GLU28:OE1	H-Acceptor
9	B:LYS24:NZ - :[001	4.84973	Electrostatic	Pi-Cation	B:LYS24:NZ	Positive	:[001	Pi-Orbitals
10	B:LYS24:NZ - :[001	4.56584	Electrostatic	Pi-Cation	B:LYS24:NZ	Positive	:[001	Pi-Orbitals
11	A:PHE55 - :[001	4.79992	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	A:PHE55	Pi-Orbitals	:[001	Pi-Orbitals
12	A:PHE55 - :[001	4.95682	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	A:PHE55	Pi-Orbitals	:[001	Pi-Orbitals
13	:[001 - B:LYS24	4.9034	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	:[001	Pi-Orbitals	B:LYS24	Alkyl
14	:[001 - B:LYS24	3.92439	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	:[001	Pi-Orbitals	B:LYS24	Alkyl

Table S5 . Interaction categories, types, and distances of molecular insertion of the aridanin molecule with bcl-52

No	Name	Distance	Category	Type	Transmitter	From Chemistry	Receiver	To Chemistry
1	C:LEU59:HN - :[011:O7	2.66143	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	C:LEU59:HN	H-Donor	:[011:O7	H-Acceptor
2	:[011:H50 - A:GLU135:OE2	2.20296	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H50	H-Donor	A:GLU135:OE2	H-Acceptor
3	:[011:H51 - B:GLN118:O	1.88929	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H51	H-Donor	B:GLN118:O	H-Acceptor
4	:[011:H57 - A:GLU136:OE1	1.75524	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H57	H-Donor	A:GLU136:OE1	H-Acceptor
5	:[011:H58 - A:GLN118:O	1.86176	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H58	H-Donor	A:GLN118:O	H-Acceptor
6	:[011:H3 - A:GLU136:OE1	2.36803	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H3	H-Donor	A:GLU136:OE1	H-Acceptor
7	:[011:H47 - A:GLU136:OE1	2.05696	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H47	H-Donor	A:GLU136:OE1	H-Acceptor
8	:[011:H48 - A:GLU135:OE2	2.63905	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H48	H-Donor	A:GLU135:OE2	H-Acceptor
9	:[011:H49 - A:GLU135:OE2	2.20748	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H49	H-Donor	A:GLU135:OE2	H-Acceptor
10	:[011:H53 - A:THR132:O	2.73	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H53	H-Donor	A:THR132:O	H-Acceptor
11	:[011:H53 - A:GLU136:OE1	2.29741	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H53	H-Donor	A:GLU136:OE1	H-Acceptor
12	:[011:H55 - B:GLN118:O	2.92944	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H55	H-Donor	B:GLN118:O	H-Acceptor
13	:[011:H56 - B:GLN118:O	1.90612	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H56	H-Donor	B:GLN118:O	H-Acceptor
14	A:LEU119 - :[011	4.8193	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:LEU119	Alkyl	:[011	Alkyl
15	A:VAL133 - :[011	4.32288	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:VAL133	Alkyl	:[011	Alkyl
16	C:LYS58 - :[011	4.88951	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	C:LYS58	Alkyl	:[011	Alkyl
17	C:LEU59 - :[011	4.66297	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	C:LEU59	Alkyl	:[011	Alkyl
18	D:LYS58 - :[011	4.42082	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	D:LYS58	Alkyl	:[011	Alkyl
19	:[011:C23 - A:VAL133	4.93528	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[011:C23	Alkyl	A:VAL133	Alkyl
20	:[011:C23 - C:LEU59	3.9209	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[011:C23	Alkyl	C:LEU59	Alkyl
21	:[011:C24 - A:LEU119	4.73918	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[011:C24	Alkyl	A:LEU119	Alkyl
22	:[011:C24 - A:ARG129	3.33266	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[011:C24	Alkyl	A:ARG129	Alkyl
23	:[011:C25 - B:VAL133	4.17451	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[011:C25	Alkyl	B:VAL133	Alkyl
24	:[011:C25 - D:LYS58	4.42097	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[011:C25	Alkyl	D:LYS58	Alkyl
25	:[011:C25 - D:LEU59	4.95138	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[011:C25	Alkyl	D:LEU59	Alkyl
26	:[011:C27 - C:LYS58	4.03309	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[011:C27	Alkyl	C:LYS58	Alkyl
27	:[011:C27 - D:LYS58	4.05433	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[011:C27	Alkyl	D:LYS58	Alkyl
28	A:PHE153 - :[011:C23	4.62203	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE153	Pi-Orbitals	:[011:C23	Alkyl

Table S6 . Interaction categories, types, and distances of molecular insertion of the doxorubicin molecule with bcl-52

No	Name	Distance	Category	Type	Transmitter	From Chemistry	Receiver Chemistry	To Chemistry
1	A:ARG127:HH11 - :[001:O1	1.849	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:ARG127:HH1	H-Donor	:[001:O1	H-Acceptor
2	B:ARG129:HH22 - :[001:O4	2.3545	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:ARG129:HH2	H-Donor	:[001:O4	H-Acceptor
3	:[001:H11 - A:GLU179:OE2	1.7693	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H11	H-Donor	A:GLU179:OE2	H-Acceptor
4	:[001:H12 - A:ARG127:O	2.2958	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H12	H-Donor	A:ARG127:O	H-Acceptor
5	:[001:H22 - A:GLU135:OE1	1.6297	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H22	H-Donor	A:GLU135:OE1	H-Acceptor
6	:[001:H24 - A:GLU135:OE1	2.2558	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H24	H-Donor	A:GLU135:OE1	H-Acceptor
7	:[001:H28 - A:HIS184:NE2	1.9273	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H28	H-Donor	A:HIS184:NE2	H-Acceptor
8	:[001:H29 - B:THR122:OG1	2.1204	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H29	H-Donor	B:THR122:OG1	H-Acceptor
9	A:TRP176:HD1 - :[001:O1	3.0908	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:TRP176:HD1	H-Donor	:[001:O1	H-Acceptor
10	A:ARG183:HD1 - :[001:O10	2.4361	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:ARG183:HD1	H-Donor	:[001:O10	H-Acceptor
11	A:HIS184:HD2 - :[001:O3	3.0535	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:HIS184:HD2	H-Donor	:[001:O3	H-Acceptor
12	B:THR122:HB - :[001:O9	2.7416	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:THR122:HB	H-Donor	:[001:O9	H-Acceptor
13	:[001:H10 - A:TRP176:O	2.182	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H10	H-Donor	A:TRP176:O	H-Acceptor
14	:[001:H16 - A:HIS184:NE2	2.2653	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H16	H-Donor	A:HIS184:NE2	H-Acceptor
15	A:ARG183:NH1 - :[001	3.3424	Electrostatic	Pi-Cation	A:ARG183:NH1	Positive	:[001	Pi-Orbitals
16	A:ARG183:NH2 - :[001	4.8265	Electrostatic	Pi-Cation	A:ARG183:NH2	Positive	:[001	Pi-Orbitals
17	:[001:H16 - A:HIS184	2.8616	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma	:[001:H16	C-H	A:HIS184	Pi-Orbitals
18	A:HIS184 - :[001	4.7987	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS184	Pi-Orbitals	:[001	Alkyl

Table S7. Interaction categories, types, and distances of molecular insertion of the aridanin molecule with DNA methyltransferase 1

No	Name	Distance	Category	Type	Transmitter	From Chemistry	Receiver	To Chemistry
1	:CYS1151:HN - :{001:O8	2.14589	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:CYS1151:HN	H-Donor	:{001:O8	H-Acceptor
2	:GLN1230:HE21 - :{001:O7	1.92495	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:GLN1230:HE21	H-Donor	:{001:O7	H-Acceptor
3	:{001:H50 - :PHE1148:O	1.61446	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:{001:H50	H-Donor	:PHE1148:O	H-Acceptor
4	:{001:H57 - :ASP1146:OD1	2.53949	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:{001:H57	H-Donor	:ASP1146:OD1	H-Acceptor
5	:GLY1150:HA2 - :{001:O3	2.29271	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:GLY1150:HA2	H-Donor	:{001:O3	H-Acceptor
6	:GLY1225:HA2 - :{001:O5	2.80182	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:GLY1225:HA2	H-Donor	:{001:O5	H-Acceptor
7	:{001:H3 - :GLU1269:OE2	2.485	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:{001:H3	H-Donor	:GLU1269:OE2	H-Acceptor
8	:{001:H48 - :SER1149:O	2.58789	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:{001:H48	H-Donor	:SER1149:O	H-Acceptor
9	:{001:H49 - :PHE1148:O	2.32813	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:{001:H49	H-Donor	:PHE1148:O	H-Acceptor
10	:{001:H55 - :ASN1580:O	2.94015	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:{001:H55	H-Donor	:ASN1580:O	H-Acceptor
11	:{001:H56 - :SER1149:O	3.06845	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:{001:H56	H-Donor	:SER1149:O	H-Acceptor
12	A:VAL529 - :{001	4.82876	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:VAL529	Alkyl	:{001	Alkyl
13	:VAL1271 - :{001	4.73347	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:VAL1271	Alkyl	:{001	Alkyl
14	:{001:C24 - A:VAL529	4.45582	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:{001:C24	Alkyl	A:VAL529	Alkyl
15	:{001:C25 - :VAL1582	4.62777	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:{001:C25	Alkyl	:VAL1582	Alkyl
16	:{001:C27 - :PRO1228	4.84148	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:{001:C27	Alkyl	:PRO1228	Alkyl

Table S8. Interaction categories, types, and distances of molecular insertion of the doxorubicin molecule with DNA methyltransferase 1

No	Name	Distance	Category	Type	Transmitter	From Chemistry	Receiver	To Chemistry
1	:GLY1226:HN - :[011:N1	2.5072	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:GLY1226:HN	H-Donor	:[011:N1	H-Acceptor
2	:VAL1582:HN - :[011:O4	2.6581	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:VAL1582:HN	H-Donor	:[011:O4	H-Acceptor
3	:[011:H12 - :ASN1580:O	2.6447	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H12	H-Donor	:ASN1580:O	H-Acceptor
4	:[011:H23 - :ASP1146:OD1	2.2355	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H23	H-Donor	:ASP1146:OD1	H-Acceptor
5	:[011:H28 - :GLY1226:O	1.7385	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H28	H-Donor	:GLY1226:O	H-Acceptor
6	:PHE1148:HA - :[011:O10	2.9112	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:PHE1148:HA	H-Donor	:[011:O10	H-Acceptor
7	:[011:H1 - :GLY1226:O	2.3200	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H1	H-Donor	:GLY1226:O	H-Acceptor
8	:[011:H10 - :PRO1227:O	2.4145	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H10	H-Donor	:PRO1227:O	H-Acceptor
9	:[011:H13 - :GLU1269:OE2	2.6510	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H13	H-Donor	:GLU1269:OE2	H-Acceptor
10	:[011:H16 - :PHE1148:O	1.8947	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H16	H-Donor	:PHE1148:O	H-Acceptor
11	:[011:H17 - :SER1149:O	2.1345	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H17	H-Donor	:SER1149:O	H-Acceptor
12	:GLU1171:OE2 - :[011	4.0637	Electrostatic	Pi-Anion	:GLU1171:OE2	Negative	:[011	Pi-Orbitals
13	:MET1172:SD - :[011	5.7927	Other	Pi-Sulfur	:MET1172:SD	Sulfur	:[011	Pi-Orbitals
14	:PRO1227:C,O;PRO1228:N - :[011	5.0703	Hydrophobic	Amide-Pi Stacked	PRO1228:N	Amide	:[011	Pi-Orbitals
15	:ALA1581 - :[011:C23	3.6713	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:ALA1581	Alkyl	:[011:C23	Alkyl
16	:[011:C24 - :MET1172	5.0196	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[011:C24	Alkyl	:MET1172	Alkyl
17	:PHE1148 - :[011:C24	4.9379	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	:PHE1148	Pi-Orbitals	:[011:C24	Alkyl
18	:[011 - :PRO1228	4.8912	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	:[011	Pi-Orbitals	:PRO1228	Alkyl
19	:[011 - :PRO1228	3.9469	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	:[011	Pi-Orbitals	:PRO1228	Alkyl
20	:[011 - :PRO1228	4.2836	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	:[011	Pi-Orbitals	:PRO1228	Alkyl

Table S9. Interaction categories, types, and distances of molecular insertion of the aridanin molecule with her2

No	Name	Distance	Category	Type	Transmitter	From Chemistry	Receiver	To Chemistry
1	A:LYS765:HZ2 - :[001:O4	2.90871	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:LYS765:HZ2	H-Donor	:[001:O4	H-Acceptor
2	B:LYS957:HZ1 - :[001:O4	2.79085	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:LYS957:HZ1	H-Donor	:[001:O4	H-Acceptor
3	:[001:H50 - A:ASP769:OD1	3.03087	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H50	H-Donor	A:ASP769:OD1	H-Acceptor
4	:[001:H51 - A:ASP769:OD1	2.11568	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H51	H-Donor	A:ASP769:OD1	H-Acceptor
5	:[001:H57 - A:ASP769:OD1	2.43916	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H57	H-Donor	A:ASP769:OD1	H-Acceptor
6	:[001:H58 - B:ARG966:O	1.65759	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H58	H-Donor	B:ARG966:O	H-Acceptor
7	B:CYS965:HA - :[001:O6	3.06743	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:CYS965:HA	H-Donor	:[001:O6	H-Acceptor
8	:[001:H48 - A:ASP769:OD1	1.621	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H48	H-Donor	A:ASP769:OD1	H-Acceptor
9	A:LYS765 - :[001	5.16673	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:LYS765	Alkyl	:[001	Alkyl
10	A:LYS765 - :[001	4.47315	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:LYS765	Alkyl	:[001	Alkyl
11	B:LYS957 - :[001	5.05925	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	B:LYS957	Alkyl	:[001	Alkyl
12	B:PRO967 - :[001	4.7155	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	B:PRO967	Alkyl	:[001	Alkyl
13	:[001:C24 - A:LYS765	3.47094	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C24	Alkyl	A:LYS765	Alkyl
14	:[001:C25 - B:ILE954	3.38125	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C25	Alkyl	B:ILE954	Alkyl

Table S10. Interaction categories, types, and distances of molecular insertion of the doxorubicin molecule with her2

No	Name	Distance	Category	Type	Transmitter	From Chemistry	Receiver	To Chemistry
1	A:TYR772:HH - :[001:O4	2.27389	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:TYR772:HH	H-Donor	:[001:O4	H-Acceptor
2	A:ILE872:HN - :[001:O11	2.86443	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:ILE872:HN	H-Donor	:[001:O11	H-Acceptor
3	B:ARG978:HH11 - :[001:O8	1.86838	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:ARG978:HH11	H-Donor	:[001:O8	H-Acceptor
4	B:ARG978:HH21 - :[001:O9	1.80229	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:ARG978:HH21	H-Donor	:[001:O9	H-Acceptor
5	B:ARG985:HH21 - :[001:O2	2.76221	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:ARG985:HH21	H-Donor	:[001:O2	H-Acceptor
6	:[001:H23 - A:ASP838:O	2.24678	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H23	H-Donor	A:ASP838:O	H-Acceptor
7	:[001:H29 - B:ASP950:OD2	2.78201	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H29	H-Donor	B:ASP950:OD2	H-Acceptor
8	:[001:H25 - A:ASP769:OD1	2.47816	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H25	H-Donor	A:ASP769:OD1	H-Acceptor
9	:[001:H27 - A:LEU768:O	2.93122	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H27	H-Donor	A:LEU768:O	H-Acceptor
10	A:TYR772 - :[001	4.24744	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi Stacked	A:TYR772	Pi-Orbitals	:[001	Pi-Orbitals
11	A:TYR772 - :[001	3.97997	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi Stacked	A:TYR772	Pi-Orbitals	:[001	Pi-Orbitals
12	A:TYR772 - :[001	4.98203	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi Stacked	A:TYR772	Pi-Orbitals	:[001	Pi-Orbitals
13	:[001:C23 - A:VAL773	3.74968	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C23	Alkyl	A:VAL773	Alkyl
14	:[001:C23 - A:VAL839	4.55988	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C23	Alkyl	A:VAL839	Alkyl
15	:[001:C23 - A:LEU869	4.65480	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C23	Alkyl	A:LEU869	Alkyl
16	:[001:C24 - B:MET953	4.17387	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C24	Alkyl	B:MET953	Alkyl
17	A:TYR772 - :[001:C23	4.36839	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR772	Pi-Orbitals	:[001:C23	Alkyl
18	A:TYR772 - :[001:C24	4.63138	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR772	Pi-Orbitals	:[001:C24	Alkyl
19	:[001 - B:MET953	5.35564	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	:[001	Pi-Orbitals	B:MET953	Alkyl

Table S11 . Interaction categories, types, and distances of molecular insertion of the aridanin molecule with mdm2

No	Name	Distance	Category	Type	Transmitter	From Chemistry	Receiver	To Chemistry
1	:{001:H50 - A:LYS60:O	2.06831	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:{001:H50	H-Donor	A:LYS60:O	H-Acceptor
2	:{001:H52 - A:LYS60:O	2.19803	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:{001:H52	H-Donor	A:LYS60:O	H-Acceptor
3	:{001:H57 - A:HIS72:O	2.02308	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:{001:H57	H-Donor	A:HIS72:O	H-Acceptor
4	:{001:H58 - B:SER32:O	1.83833	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:{001:H58	H-Donor	B:SER32:O	H-Acceptor
5	B:SER36:HA - :{001:O7	2.99019	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:SER36:HA	H-Donor	:{001:O7	H-Acceptor
6	:{001:H3 - A:ASN75:O	2.51379	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:{001:H3	H-Donor	A:ASN75:O	H-Acceptor
7	A:LYS60 - :{001	5.35578	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:LYS60	Alkyl	:{001	Alkyl
8	A:PRO77 - :{001	5.34816	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:PRO77	Alkyl	:{001	Alkyl
9	B:LYS35 - :{001	5.07261	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	B:LYS35	Alkyl	:{001	Alkyl
10	B:LYS35 - :{001	4.85843	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	B:LYS35	Alkyl	:{001	Alkyl
11	:{001:C27 - A:PRO77	4.09315	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:{001:C27	Alkyl	A:PRO77	Alkyl
12	:{001:C27 - B:PRO28	4.89307	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:{001:C27	Alkyl	B:PRO28	Alkyl
13	:{001:C27 - B:LEU31	4.63446	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:{001:C27	Alkyl	B:LEU31	Alkyl

Table S12. Interaction categories, types, and distances of molecular insertion of the doxorubicin molecule with mdm2

No	Name	Distance	Category	Type	Transmitter	From Chemistry	Receiver	To Chemistry
1	A:TYR56:HH - :[001:O10	2.6448	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:TYR56:HH	H-Donor	:[001:O10	H-Acceptor
2	A:LYS60:HZ1 - :[001:O10	1.9432	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:LYS60:HZ1	H-Donor	:[001:O10	H-Acceptor
3	A:LYS60:HZ3 - :[001:O6	1.6399	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:LYS60:HZ3	H-Donor	:[001:O6	H-Acceptor
4	:[001:H22 - B:LEU29:O	2.9904	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H22	H-Donor	B:LEU29:O	H-Acceptor
5	:[001:H29 - B:SER32:O	2.2042	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H29	H-Donor	B:SER32:O	H-Acceptor
6	:[001:H1 - A:SER32:O	2.7334	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H1	H-Donor	A:SER32:O	H-Acceptor
7	:[001:H18 - A:LEU29:O	2.8861	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H18	H-Donor	A:LEU29:O	H-Acceptor
8	:[001:H25 - A:ASP76:OD1	1.9522	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H25	H-Donor	A:ASP76:OD1	H-Acceptor
9	:[001:C23 - A:LEU29	3.8316	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C23	Alkyl	A:LEU29	Alkyl
10	:[001:C23 - A:LEU33	4.5156	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C23	Alkyl	A:LEU33	Alkyl
11	:[001:C23 - A:LEU81	4.867	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C23	Alkyl	A:LEU81	Alkyl
12	:[001:C23 - B:LEU29	4.2059	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C23	Alkyl	B:LEU29	Alkyl
13	:[001:C24 - A:LYS60	4.5765	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C24	Alkyl	A:LYS60	Alkyl
14	:[001:C24 - A:PRO77	4.4872	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C24	Alkyl	A:PRO77	Alkyl
15	:[001 - B:LYS35	4.9617	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	:[001	Pi-Orbitals	B:LYS35	Alkyl
16	:[001 - B:LYS35	5.1946	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	:[001	Pi-Orbitals	B:LYS35	Alkyl

Table S13. Interaction categories, types, and distances of molecular insertion of the aridanin molecule with DNA gyrase

No	Name	Distance	Category	Type	Transmitter	From Chemistry	Receiver	To Chemistry
1	:[001:H45 - A:VAL71:O	1,84161	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H45	H-Donor	A:VAL71:O	H-Acceptor
2	:[001:H46 - A:VAL43:O	1,64827	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H46	H-Donor	A:VAL43:O	H-Acceptor
3	A:THR165:HB - :[001:O4	2,1058	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:THR165:HB	H-Donor	:[001:O4	H-Acceptor
4	:[001:H53 - A:VAL71:O	2,06335	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H53	H-Donor	A:VAL71:O	H-Acceptor
5	:[001:H57 - A:THR165:O	2,02918	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H57	H-Donor	A:THR165:O	H-Acceptor
6	A:PRO79 - :[001	3,75978	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:PRO79	Alkyl	:[001	Alkyl
7	A:PRO79 - :[001	4,40213	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:PRO79	Alkyl	:[001	Alkyl
8	:[001:C24 - A:PRO79	4,08701	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C24	Alkyl	A:PRO79	Alkyl

Table S14. Interaction categories, types, and distances of molecular insertion of the Doxorubicin molecule with DNA gyrase

No	Name	Distance	Category	Type	Transmitter	From Chemistry	Receiver	To Chemistry
1	A:GLY77:HN - :[001:O11	2,11646	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:GLY77:HN	H-Donor	:[001:O11	H-Acceptor
2	A:THR165:HG1 - :[001:O11	2,20008	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:THR165:HG1	H-Donor	:[001:O11	H-Acceptor
3	:[001:H11 - A:GLY77:O	2,08641	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H11	H-Donor	A:GLY77:O	H-Acceptor
4	:[001:H12 - A:ASP73:OD1	1,65674	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H12	H-Donor	A:ASP73:OD1	H-Acceptor
5	:[001:H22 - A:VAL43:O	2,35578	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H22	H-Donor	A:VAL43:O	H-Acceptor
6	:[001:H23 - A:VAL71:O	2,25273	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H23	H-Donor	A:VAL71:O	H-Acceptor
7	:[001:H23 - A:THR165:O	2,41714	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H23	H-Donor	A:THR165:O	H-Acceptor
8	:[001:H29 - A:GLU50:OE1	2,29056	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H29	H-Donor	A:GLU50:OE1	H-Acceptor
9	:[001:H17 - A:VAL71:O	3,07854	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H17	H-Donor	A:VAL71:O	H-Acceptor
10	A:ASN46:HD21 - :[001	3,16164	Hydrogen Bond	Pi-Donor Hydrogen Bond	A:ASN46:HD21	H-Donor	:[001	Pi-Orbitals
11	:[001:C23 - A:VAL43	3,09327	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C23	Alkyl	A:VAL43	Alkyl
12	:[001:C23 - A:VAL120	3,86377	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C23	Alkyl	A:VAL120	Alkyl
13	:[001:C23 - A:VAL167	3,37195	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C23	Alkyl	A:VAL167	Alkyl
14	:[001:C24 - A:ILE90	4,81428	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C24	Alkyl	A:ILE90	Alkyl
15	:[001 - A:ILE78	5,36164	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	:[001	Pi-Orbitals	A:ILE78	Alkyl

Table S15. Interaction categories, types, and distances of molecular insertion of the aridanin molecule with glucosamine-6-phosphate

No	Name	Distance	Category	Type	Transmitter	From Chemistry	Receiver	To Chemistry
1	A:CYS300:HN - :[001:O7	1,72377	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:CYS300:HN	H-Donor	: [001:O7	H-Acceptor
2	A:SER303:HG - : [001:O7	2,86063	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:SER303:HG	H-Donor	: [001:O7	H-Acceptor
3	A:GLN348:HE21 - : [001:O8	1,78134	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:GLN348:HE21	H-Donor	: [001:O8	H-Acceptor
4	: [001:H45 - A:SER349:OG	1,68331	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	: [001:H45	H-Donor	A:SER349:OG	H-Acceptor
5	: [001:H50 - A:THR352:OG1	2,10553	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	: [001:H50	H-Donor	A:THR352:OG1	H-Acceptor
6	: [001:H54 - A:LYS603:O	2,42483	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	: [001:H54	H-Donor	A:LYS603:O	H-Acceptor
7	A:SER303:HB2 - : [001:O7	1,72851	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:SER303:HB2	H-Donor	: [001:O7	H-Acceptor
8	: [001:H51 - A:CYS300:O	2,81639	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	: [001:H51	H-Donor	A:CYS300:O	H-Acceptor
9	: [001:H56 - A:LYS603:O	1,34503	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	: [001:H56	H-Donor	A:LYS603:O	H-Acceptor
10	A:LYS487 - : [001	5,07576	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:LYS487	Alkyl	: [001	Alkyl
11	A:LEU601 - : [001	4,52648	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:LEU601	Alkyl	: [001	Alkyl
12	A:ALA602 - : [001:C28	4,232	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:ALA602	Alkyl	: [001:C28	Alkyl
13	A:VAL605 - : [001	5,21604	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:VAL605	Alkyl	: [001	Alkyl
14	: [001:C26 - A:LEU484	4,03535	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	: [001:C26	Alkyl	A:LEU484	Alkyl
15	: [001:C28 - A:VAL605	4,56474	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	: [001:C28	Alkyl	A:VAL605	Alkyl

Table S16. Interaction categories, types, and distances of molecular insertion of the doxorubicin molecule with glucosamine-6-phosphate

No	Name	Distance	Category	Type	Transmitter	From Chemistry	Receiver	To Chemist
1	A:CYS300:HG - :[001:O6	2,55275	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:CYS300:HG	H-Donor	:001:O6	H-Acceptor
2	A:SER303:HN - :[001:O3	2,37258	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:SER303:HN	H-Donor	:001:O3	H-Acceptor
3	A:SER349:HN - :[001:O5	2,02731	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:SER349:HN	H-Donor	:001:O5	H-Acceptor
4	A:SER401:HN - :[001:O2	1,70515	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:SER401:HN	H-Donor	:001:O2	H-Acceptor
5	A:SER401:HN - :[001:O11	2,59347	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:SER401:HN	H-Donor	:001:O11	H-Acceptor
6	A:LYS603:HZ3 - :[001:O11	2,72431	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:LYS603:HZ3	H-Donor	:001:O11	H-Acceptor
7	:001:H11 - A:ALA602:O	1,64075	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:001:H11	H-Donor	A:ALA602:O	H-Acceptor
8	:001:H12 - A:GLU488:OE2	2,29006	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:001:H12	H-Donor	A:GLU488:OE2	H-Acceptor
9	:001:H22 - A:SER347:OG	1,73117	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:001:H22	H-Donor	A:SER347:OG	H-Acceptor
10	A:SER303:HB2 - :[001:O4	2,59005	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:SER303:HB2	H-Donor	:001:O4	H-Acceptor
11	A:SER347:HA - :[001:O4	2,49775	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:SER347:HA	H-Donor	:001:O4	H-Acceptor
12	A:SER401:HB2 - :[001:O2	2,51213	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:SER401:HB2	H-Donor	:001:O2	H-Acceptor
13	:001:H9 - A:VAL399:O	2,04975	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:001:H9	H-Donor	A:VAL399:O	H-Acceptor
14	:001:H13 - A:SER303:OG	2,08521	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:001:H13	H-Donor	A:SER303:OG	H-Acceptor
15	:001:H17 - A:THR352:OG1	1,81272	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:001:H17	H-Donor	A:THR352:OG1	H-Acceptor
16	:001:H26 - A:VAL605:O	2,96745	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:001:H26	H-Donor	A:VAL605:O	H-Acceptor
17	:001:H27 - A:ASP354:OD2	2,95799	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	:001:H27	H-Donor	A:ASP354:OD2	H-Acceptor
18	A:CYS300:C,O;GLY301:N - :[001	4,39642	Hydrophobic	Amide-Pi Stacked	GLY301:N	Amide	:001	Pi-Orbitals
19	:001:C24 - A:CYS300	4,51878	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:001:C24	Alkyl	A:CYS300	Alkyl
20	:001:C24 - A:VAL605	3,45265	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:001:C24	Alkyl	A:VAL605	Alkyl
21	:001 - A:CYS300	4,6954	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	:001	Pi-Orbitals	A:CYS300	Alkyl
22	:001 - A:VAL605	4,69871	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	:001	Pi-Orbitals	A:VAL605	Alkyl
23	:001 - A:CYS300	4,60675	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	:001	Pi-Orbitals	A:CYS300	Alkyl
24	:001 - A:VAL605	5,42467	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	:001	Pi-Orbitals	A:VAL605	Alkyl

Table S17. Interaction categories, types, and distances of molecular insertion of the aridanin molecule with DD-Peptidase

No	Name	Distance	Category	Type	Transmitter	From Chemistry	Receiver	To Chemistry
1	A:ARG285:HH2 - :[001:O7	2,11304	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:ARG285:HH2	H-Donor	:[001:O7	H-Acceptor
2	A:GLN303:HE22 - :[001:O8	2,12817	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:GLN303:HE22	H-Donor	:[001:O8	H-Acceptor
3	A:ASN327:HN - :[001:O4	2,87615	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:ASN327:HN	H-Donor	:[001:O4	H-Acceptor
4	:[001:H50 - A:THR123:OG1	2,3708	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[001:H50	H-Donor	A:THR123:OG1	H-Acceptor
5	A:ASN327:HA - :[001:O5	2,9447	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:ASN327:HA	H-Donor	:[001:O5	H-Acceptor
6	:[001:C24 - A:LEU332	4,19814	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	:[001:C24	Alkyl	A:LEU332	Alkyl
7	A:PHE120 - :[001:C25	3,74287	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE120	Pi-Orbitals	:[001:C25	Alkyl
8	A:TRP233 - :[001	4,75389	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP233	Pi-Orbitals	:[001	Alkyl
9	A:TRP233 - :[001:C25	4,73505	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP233	Pi-Orbitals	:[001:C25	Alkyl
10	A:TRP233 - :[001:C27	4,94479	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP233	Pi-Orbitals	:[001:C27	Alkyl

Table S18. Interaction categories, types, and distances of molecular insertion of the doxorubicin molecule with DD-Peptidase

No	Name	Distance	Category	Type	Transmitter	From Chemistry	Receiver	To Chemistry
1	A:ASN161:HD22 - :[011:O5	2.20241	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:ASN161:HD22	H-Donor	:[011:O5	H-Acceptor
2	A:GLN303:HE22 - :[011:O1	2.14227	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:GLN303:HE22	H-Donor	:[011:O1	H-Acceptor
3	:[011:H11 - A:THR123:O	2.22714	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H11	H-Donor	A:THR123:O	H-Acceptor
4	:[011:H29 - A:THR123:OG1	2.05207	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	:[011:H29	H-Donor	A:THR123:OG1	H-Acceptor
5	A:ASN117:HA - :[011:O6	2.3826	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:ASN117:HA	H-Donor	:[011:O6	H-Acceptor
6	A:ASN117:HA - :[011:O10	2.66286	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:ASN117:HA	H-Donor	:[011:O10	H-Acceptor
7	A:PHE120 - :[011	5.895	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	A:PHE120	Pi-Orbitals	:[011	Pi-Orbitals
8	A:TRP233 - :[011:C23	4.38621	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP233	Pi-Orbitals	:[011:C23	Alkyl